

USING ROLE PLAYS AND SIMULATION ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING SPEAKING

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Annotation: This article discusses the role of various games and role-playing games in improving children's speech.

Key words: psychology, communication, communicative activity, successful teaching, role-playing.

The study of the emergence and development of a child's speech is relevant not only from the point of view of psychology, but also of personal and social importance.[1] Speech is a structural element of communicative activity, which, in turn, plays a decisive role in the development of a child's cognitive activity. Through communication and speech, the child learns to receive information from the treasury of the socio-historical experience of mankind. The development of oral monologic speech at preschool age lays the foundation for successful teaching at school.

One of the main tasks of the game for the development of speech of a preschool child is to enrich the child's words, to master concepts, to understand the polysemy of used words and their semantic shades. Speech activity develops in the games, interest and attention to the mother tongue is cultivated.

The game is an activity aimed at educating the child correctly in all aspects. The game develops a person as a mature generation. A toy is a special object of this thing, which helps the child to learn about the goal and to direct it to this goal. Many research scientists have proven that through toys, children get into situations that they will face in the future and learn how to get out of them. By playing with toys, children get to know the world around them. Children want relationships between them, cultures of treating each other, talking among themselves like adults. Through toys, the child can explain what he wants to say to you and others. They enrich their knowledge of existence through toys. The difference between a game and a toy is that through the game, children learn to adapt to different environments. Children themselves participate in the game. In the game, we can find out what is going on in children's psyche and

thoughts. Through the game, speech and communication culture develops among children.

Toys attract children with their variety. Each child plays with different toys. You can find out about the child's inner world by looking at what kind of toy he is playing with. The relationship with the child in the family is also expressed by the child playing with toys. Children should be taught to name pictures of objects belonging to different categories in order to increase their vocabulary. For this purpose, it is possible to name objects belonging to categories such as fruits, vegetables, domestic animals, wild animals, professions, colors, geometric shapes, divide words into syllables, and talk about the symbols of objects. After naming pictures of objects, the child should be able to summarize these words. Role-playing is a teaching strategy that enables students to engage with the topic in a way that is not possible in a traditional method. It requires the students to participate in a play to represent a specific role or character. It is an important way for the students to practice speaking. In addition, this way gives the students chance to communicate with other people provisionally. Role-play is a favorite activity in speaking class. In role-play, students need extra time to prepare what they have to say. The role gives some opportunities for the students to use the script with its difficulties. The teachers can guide the role-play. The responsiveness to the complexity is the technique to decide the score. This technique makes the test-takers more simple, intensive, and responsive. To establish role-playing as a strategy for language development inside the EFL curriculum, a study of theories of language and ideas of second language acquisition is an absolute necessity. According to , three critical theoretical perspectives are considered when constructing a language teaching technique: structural, functional, and interactional. According to structural theory, language is composed of grammatical units such as phrases, clauses, sentences, and affixes. According to functional theory, language is a mode of communication that can be informative, emotive, persuasive, or social. According to interactional theory, a language is a tool for establishing interpersonal interactions and carrying out social transactions between individuals and society. Each perspective has a distinct role to play in the development of language education approaches. The final two theories lay the theoretical groundwork for Communicative Language Instruction

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